

INNOVATION IN TERMINOLOGY WITHIN MILITARY EDUCATION

Mamedova R.

National Defense University of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Abstract

The influence of the military-political factor on the process of developing military terminology is closely connected with global conflicts, military cooperation, and technological changes. All this draws special attention to the importance of in-depth research into military terminology, which has already gone beyond the frames of application in special fields of communication and entered everyday communication as a result of information from mass media. While describing the emphatic character of their development, military terms should be classified according to the usage criteria, ways of formation, structural features, and features of stylistic functioning. Different linguistic means to form the military terms are affixation, compounding, abbreviation, and conversion. The findings have brought into focus what effect technological and scientific advancement has had on the increase of military lexicon.

Keywords: military terminology, English language, military education, term classification, word formation, globalization.

Description: (INTRODUCTION)

Military-political issues are perhaps the most popular topic in news releases and analytical articles: states and governments of leading countries, in order to expand their influence, are constantly developing and updating projects related to the creation of weapons and military technologies. In many regions of the world, ethnic, religious, and armed conflicts exist or are emerging. However, the trend of globalization and internationalization leads to the fact that most states of the world are trying to maintain international security and strategic stability by intensifying military cooperation in various forms and at different levels. All these factors influence the development of military terminology, which requires in-depth and comprehensive research at the present stage of its development.

The beginning of the 21st century is marked by global world events: we are witnessing important migration processes, creating precedents in politics and legislation, the collapse and emergence of states. Many of these events are military in nature, and the capabilities of the media make it possible to convey the details of what happened to every home and family. Special television channels talk about modern types of weapons and demonstrated by the military films. Anyone can find descriptions of various unclassified types of weapons on the Internet. In other words, military vocabulary has long gone beyond the limits of highly specialized use and entered the vocabulary of the common man. Recognizing military terminology as the most the moving part of the military sublanguage, domestic and foreign linguists are exploring various aspects of the military terminological arsenal: from the structure of the term and its translation [5], systematization and unification to its cognitive aspects [3]. Permanent and consistent development of military-defense sphere gives a powerful impetus to the development of the linguistic component, which undoubtedly entails the formation of new areas of study, to which already existing scientific paradigms are successfully applied and developed new. The theoretical significance of such research lies in the expansion and streamlining of general linguistic knowledge, while practical application refers to both

the military sphere, as well as the social and journalistic sphere.

The presence of an army is a mandatory characteristic of any modern sovereign state. A distinctive feature of an army is its size and the degree of its combat effectiveness. The composition of the army, traditions and the attitude of society towards the army are the most important reasons that influence the formation and further development of military terminology. It should be noted that military terminology is replenished not only in times of various kinds of conflicts, but also during military reforms and transformations. The secrecy and closeness of the army form the prerequisites for the emergence and development of military language. The concept term comes from the Latin 'terminus' and is translated as 'limit, end'.

The main difference between the terminological vocabulary from non-terminological is its maximum abstractness, unambiguity, internationality, logic and semantics. Thus, the term means a word or phrase fixed behind a specific concept in the system of concepts of a given field of science or technology. Classifying terms British maritime law from the point of view of structure, A.E. Fedotova shares them into the following types: 1) root terms, the basis of which coincides with the root; 2) derived terms consisting of a stem and affixes; 3) compound terms formed by adding two or more stems; 4) terminological combinations [2].

Military terms can be classified as follows:

I. By sphere of use (various types of troops, i.e., staff, general tactical, organizational, military topographical, command formation).

Terms of various branches of the military - terms that are used to describe concepts in armed forces formations: units, formations, associations, institutions, establishments, organizations and governing bodies. For example, '*artillery*', '*infantry*', '*radio technical troops*', '*air force*', '*airborne troops*'.

Staff terms are terms that are widely used in military personnel management bodies. For example, '*headquarters*', '*staff car*', '*personnel*'.

General tactical terms - terms that are used when solving general tactical problems, conducting combined arms combat and its preparation. For example,

'defense', *provost corps* 'field gendarmerie', 'offensive'.

Organizational terms are terms that are used in various units of military forces. For example, 'unit', 'battalion', 'division', 'company'.

Military topographical terms are terms that are used in terrain study, orientation, target designation, and taking measurements on the ground. For example, *topographic map*, *cartography*, *land survey*, 'aerial photography'.

Command and drill terms are terms that are used in drill training and command speech of military personnel. For example, *Arms, port!* 'Weapons to the chest!'; *Eyes, right!* 'Turn to the right!'.

II. By method of formation (morphological word formation, abbreviations);

Methods of morphological word formation of commonly used vocabulary in English are characteristic and in the formation of terminological vocabulary from any field of scientific knowledge, including for the formation of military terms [4]

Morphological word formation is the main way word formation and includes the following methods: affixation, compounding, abbreviation and conversion.

- affixation is a method of word formation that allows you to create new terms by attaching word-forming affixes to the stems of various parts of speech. For example, *maintainability*, *surveillance*, *deterrence*, *reunion*.

- compounding is a method of word formation that allows you to form new words by combining the stems of two or more words. For example, *aircraft*, *breakthrough*, *battlewise*.

- an abbreviation is the omission of individual letters and syllables in a word, and sometimes the removal of a significant part of the word except for individual letters. For example, *Svc Pit* (*service platoon*) 'service platoon', *sub* is derived from 'submarine', *radome* from *radar dome* 'antenna radome Radar'.

- conversion is a very common type of word formation in military terminology of the English language, in which belonging to a certain part of speech, a word, without changing its original form, acquires the meaning of another part of speech. For example,

shell > to *shell*; *blockade* > to *blockade*;

rocket > to *rocket*; *mortar* > to *mortar*.

III. By structure (one-part, two-part, multi-part);

T.I.Arbekova defines vocabulary, formed in this way, as 'complex formations' consisting of a few words [1]. Examples in the following terminological units can serve in the military sphere: the concept of 'aircraft carrier' - an aircraft carrier, formed from two words 'aircraft' and 'carrier'; 'combat management system' - a combat management system consisting of three words: 'combat' - battle, 'management' - man-

agement, 'system' - system; term 'man-portable surface-to-air missile' - portable anti-aircraft missile system.

The basis of the military terminology of the English language is made up of single-component and multi-component nominative units, which are mainly represented by substantive compounds. For example, *battle* - *battle field* - *battlefield interdiction* - *battlefield interdiction line* - *battlefield air interdiction*.

IV. By stylistic characteristics (neutral and emotionally charged lexical units).

It should be noted that military terms are usually presented lexical units that are neutral in emotional connotation. However, this classification should be given according to stylistic characteristics, since emotionally charged lexical units in the military sphere denote the same concepts as neutral lexical units.

Emotional coloring means an emotional attitude to the concept named by the word associated with the meaning of the word. Examples of emotionally charged military vocabulary in the English language are the following words: *push-button war*, *trigger-happy* 'shooting indiscriminately', *slick ship* 'unarmed helicopter'.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be noted that the development of science and technology, conducting new developments in the military sphere, improving existing models' equipment and weapons is reflected in lexical composition of the language. Pursuit to accurate and concise transmission of information, characteristic of both oral and for written speech, allows you to identify most common methods information of complex terms, as well as certain trends in the use of military terms in texts.

References

1. Arbekova T.I. (1977). *Leksikologiya angliyskogo yazyka (prakticheskiy kurs)* [Lexicology of the English language (practical course)]. Moscow, Vysshaya shkola Publ., 240 p.
2. Fedotova A. Ye. (2019). [Typology of English maritime law terms as an indicator of the systemic nature of the given terminology]. In: *Vestnik Moskovskogo gosudarstvennogo oblastnogo universiteta. Seriya: Lingvis tika* [Bulletin of the Moscow Region State University. Series: Linguistics], no. 3, pp. 45–53. (DOI: 10.18384/2310-712X-2019-3-45-53).
3. Georgieva V. (2015). *Systematization of Military Terminology: Mission (Im) Possible?* (URL: <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/274711085>).
4. Levitskiy Yu. A. (2016). *Morfologiya angliyskogo yazyka* [Morphology of the English language]. Moscow, LKI Publ., 136 p.
5. Wilson A. (2008). *Military Terminology and the English Language*. (URL: <http://homes.chass.utoronto.ca/~cpercy/>).